

назвою «Вопрас & Рагг», де використовується досить оригінальна та нова подача коктейлів. За допомогою спеціального устаткування його перетворюють у пару, після чого, гості не п'ють, а вдихають його.

Шеф кухар ресторану «Holt», що в Рейк'явіку, пропонує гостям обід на діючому вулкані, при чому стіл розташований біля самого кратера, а страви готують на розпеченій лаві.

Іншим прикладом є заклад у Мюнхені «Wash & Coffee», що поєднує в собі пральню та кав'ярню.

В Італії у ресторані «Street Dinner» пропонують відгадати кілька загадок щоб зробити замовлення та отримати його. Відвідувач залишає свій номер телефону, на який він отримує подальші вказівки крок за кроком [3].

Аналіз тенденцій на сучасному економічному ринку свідчить про те, що одними з найважливіших інновацій у ресторанному господарстві є інформаційно-комп'ютерні технології, а також нововведення у приготуванні страв чи зміні їх класичної інтерпретації.

Врахування світових тенденцій розвитку нових технологій в зарубіжних країнах дозволяє

українським закладам ресторанного господарства оцінити свої можливості та впровадити нові технології відповідно до сучасних тенденцій.

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SAFETY SYSTEM FOR AUTOMATION OF THE OIL CLEANING PROCESS

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Abstract

Since oil refining processes, including the process of petroleum products alkalization, are carried out with the participation of flammable, combustible and toxic substances, safety regulations must be observed when designing such objects. According to the law, it is required to pass an examination of projects being prepared at the moment in the Emergency Situations Ministry. Therefore, safety issues arise at these objects, as well as in the design of special explosive and fire hazardous processes [1].

It is necessary to develop a technical support base for an automated control system capable of increasing the material efficiency of a technological unit for cleaning these oil fractions from organic acids, which is of great importance in the world economy. From this point of view, it is important to develop information and algorithmic support of the automated control system for the apparatus of a technological unit.

To achieve the most effective values of both qualitative and economic indicators, various optimization methods and optimal control are used, depending on the type of apparatuses used in the technological processes of production and their interconnection schemes [2÷5].

Keywords: refining process, technological object, safety system, control cabinet, control system, technological process, programmable logic controller.

The safety systems of technological objects usually include: Fire & Gas systems (fire alarm, automatic fire extinguishing, gas detection and elimination of gas contamination) and ESD systems (automatic emergency shutdown). As the name implies, these systems solve the issues of signaling and eliminating fires and gas contamination, as well as ensuring the process safety when an emergency is approaching.

It should be noted that these systems are located in two separate control cabinets and each has an

independent control algorithm. Each cabinet contains a programmable logic controller (PLC) and its modules that process signals from the sensors of the corresponding system and generate control commands. The output signals of this controller go to fire extinguishing devices, boxes located at the outlet of fire gas cylinders, fans that exclude gas evolution, alarm sirens, a control valve that ensures process safety. Due to security requirements, it is mandatory to have a redundant controller in each system cabinet. In case of failure of the main controller, control is automatically

transferred to the backup controller. Also, each system cabinet must be provided with an uninterruptible power supply. The protection degree, which determines the control cabinets resistance to dust and moisture, must be at least IP 66 (provided that they are placed in enclosed spaces) [6].

In the existing system, each separator has valves that prevent pressure build-up and open into the gas system. Given that the process proceeds at relatively low pressure and temperature, shut-off valves are designed to be placed at the inlet and outlet of the technological product line, as well as in the lines between the alkalization separators for different types of products (gasoline, kerosene and diesel fuel).

It should be noted that in this article, equipment with safety levels SIL2 and SIL3 (for example, pressure alarm, level alarm, PLC, etc.) is taken as an ESD system, and process equipment must also have this level, otherwise only the automatic part it would be pointless to use ESD systems. This process must be carried out comprehensively. The sensors of the ESD system play a backup role, that is, if the sensor of the automatic control system fails, this system insures it [7, 8].

Fire&Gas field equipment includes smoke, heat, flame and gas detectors, fire detectors, sirens, fire extinguishers, robotic carts (which provide laser guidance to a fire) and fans.

Although these systems are located in separate control cabinets and have independent algorithms, at the top level they are integrated with each other into a single Centralized Control and Control System. When a fire occurs on any line, this event is recorded by fire detectors and transmitted to the Fire & Gas system, which generates the appropriate control signals on the PLC of this system to take appropriate measures to extinguish the fire, and at the same time this information is transmitted to the ESD system, which leads to to close the valve in the line where the gas is leaking. Another example: when there is a gas leak in any line, the pressure drops, and this is signaled by the pressure sensor of the ESD system, and this line is closed, at the same time this information is transmitted to the Fire&Gas system, and if the technological process line is in a closed room, Fans are turned on to eliminate gas contamination.

The use of the above systems to protect oil refining processes from existing threats is technically and economically justified. These systems can remain stable for years in a normal process, but once they are up and running, varying degrees accidents are prevented, which exceeds all the costs associated with the these systems implementation.

After completion of the fractions purification from organic acids, the purified kerosene is stored in tanks in the commodity park. In industry, kerosene is stored in large metal containers, but commercially it is also packaged in small quantities. For this, metal containers are used. Since kerosene is a non-volatile gaseous substance, there is no need for pressurized storage containers. In addition, due to its high flammability, it must be handled as a hazardous flammable substance.

Part of the remaining oil fractions that are not processed into kerosene can be used in other activity areas, for example, as a lubricant. In addition, some contaminants from the purification process are sold. These include some aromatic compounds such as paraffin. Standards for kerosene and other petroleum products are set by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and the American Petroleum Institute (API).

As demand for kerosene and its by-products increases, new methods for extracting and sweetening kerosene are becoming increasingly important.

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